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URDU STUDIES 3

Peer-Reviewed Bilingual Research Journal

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Guest Editor
Dr. Mehr Afshan Farooqi

Editor
Dr. Arshad Masood Hashmi

Department of Urdu
Jai Prakash University
Chhapra (India)

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DR. MEHR AFSHAN FAROOQI

Associate Professor
Department of Middle Eastern
& South Asian Languages & Cultures
University of Virginia, Charlottesville, VA 22904

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Jai Prakash University, Chapra (India)

Assistant Editor

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Associate Professor, Department of Urdu
Jai Prakash University, Chapra (India)

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Contributors

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Prof. (Dr.) Marcia Hermansen, Professor & Director, Islamic World Studies; Professor, Theology Department, Loyola University, Chicago, United States

Dr. Mehr Afshan Farooqi, Associate Professor, Department of Middle Eastern & South Asian Languages & Cultures, University of Virginia, Charlottesville, VA, United States

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Dr. Haris Qadeer, Assistant Professor, Department of English, university of Delhi, Delhi, India

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Dr. Jawaid Rahmani, Assistant Professor in Urdu, Rabindranath Tagore School of Indian Language & Cultural Studies, Assam University, Silchar, Assam, India

Dr. Raghbat Shamim Malik (tr.), Assistant Professor, Department of Urdu, P. N. College (a Constituent unit of Jai Prakash University), Parsa, Saran, India

Syed Naseer Husain Khan Khayal (Late), Azimabad, Patna, India

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Guest Editor: Dr. Mehr Afshan Farooqi

Associate Professor

Department of Middle Eastern
& South Asian Languages & Cultures

University of Virginia, Charlottesville, VA 22904

<https://www.rekhta.org/authors/mehr-afshan-farooqi/ebooks>

Chief Editor: Dr. Arshad Masood Hashmi

Professor & Head, Department of Urdu

Jai Prakash University, Chapra, India

Email: hashmiam68@gmail.com

www.arshadhashmi.academia.edu

<https://www.rekhta.org/authors/arshad-masood-hashmi/ebooks>

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The articles included in Urdu Studies are of research / critical nature. It is not necessary for the Editorial Advisory Board to agree with them. Utmost care has been taken to ensure that they do not conflict with our national interest. Despite this precaution, if such an aspect is observed, the authors will be solely responsible for it.

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EDITORIAL

We live in a highly literate world. Communication technology has opened possibilities of interaction that were unimaginable even a decade ago. Digital access has revolutionized reception of knowledge. Nonetheless, print in the form of books, journals, magazines etc. has managed to hang on in this race for several reasons—it is tangible, it is qualitative, and thus it literally carries more weight than online publications.

In the last fifty years, the complexion of Urdu Studies as an academic discipline has changed remarkably. In the subcontinent, Urdu departments at universities have shrunk but interest in Urdu as the language of culture has grown. There is a generation of scholars who work in Urdu, or whose research area is Urdu but who write in English. Translation of Urdu literary works into English has received a much-needed boost from publishers. Bilingualism is the order of the day. The present journal's bilingual format brings together a range of

scholarship belonging to the Urdu sphere. The Urdu and English sections balance one another in content. I will introduce the Urdu section first.

The Urdu opens with one of Urdu's senior most scholars, Dr Satyapal Anand, who reminisces a visit with Dr Mushfiq Khwaja. His essay invokes the tradition of *roznamachah* and *safarnamah*. Both genres became popular in Urdu. Then we have a cluster of thoughtful articles on the critical importance of metaphor in poetry ranging from the complexities of Ghalib to Irfan Siddiqui. Dr Sarvarul Hoda's article gives us a comparative view of two great scholars' opinions on Ghalib. Kalimuddin Ahmad's estimation of Ghalib's genius examines the poet's creative temperament with that of his contemporary, Mirza Rafi Sauda. According to Kalimuddin Ahmad, a poet's greatness lies in his ability to bring emotions and ideas together. But Ghalib's poetry is lacking in flow; nor does it have Mir's depth of emotion. Shamsur Rahman Faruqi's pathbreaking study of Ghalib is not limited to a textual analysis. Hoda argues that Faruqi was concerned with such small details as the controversy around Abdus Samad, Ghalib's putative tutor. Faruqi also attributes Ghalib's curiosity and restlessness to the exigencies of the times in which the poet lived and wrote. Dr Sarvarul Hoda shows how Faruqi's critical method was not limited to reified textual analysis.

Dr Najiba Arif's scholarly essay introduces us to an unpublished manuscript that she discovered at the Bodleian Library in Oxford. The manuscript is a *tazkirah* compiled by Abdul Ghafoor Nassakh a well-known poet, anthologist of the late nineteenth century. Nassakh's *tazkirah* sheds light on several pupils of Khwaja Haidar Ali Atish of Lucknow.

Dr Nasir Abbas Naiyyar's thought provoking, erudite essay expounds on the role of metaphor in meaning creation. Comparing the use of metaphor by contemporary poets with that of classical poets, Naiyyar makes the point that metaphor in the end is couched in language. Modernists might utilize metaphor to look inwards and

portray the struggles of their individual selves while classicists used metaphor for metaphysical abstractions.

Dr Anisur Rahman's "*Hindustani Adab, Tasavvur aur Tanavur*" gives us a bird's eye view of the complexities of what Indian literature might comprise. He also points to new ways of reading and receiving Hindustani literature.

The journal has a veritable bouquet of articles in the English. The English section's jewel is Professor Marcia Hermansen's overview of Khwaja Hasan Nizami's *Krishna Biti*. Khwaja Hasan Nizami, a Sufi of the Chishtiya Silsila was a pioneer of Urdu prose style. Biography, autobiography, and diary writing were some of the genres where his innovative prose style was displayed. As Professor Hermansen has shown, Khwaja Nizami's *Krishna Biti* pays tribute to the shared Hindu-Muslim cultural symbiosis that is the body and soul of the subcontinent. Most interesting is his metaphysical reading of Radha and Krishna's love and how he connects the flute with sufistic analogy.

Dr Fatima Rizvi has been working steadily in the field of gender studies. Her contribution on women's journals is well researched. Dr Rosie Llewellyn Jones tribute to Dr Fakhir Husain is a reminder of the latter's many contributions to Urdu as a translator. Dr Husain, a psychiatrist had deep connections with Lucknow that continued to the end of his life. Dr Husain's translation of Abdul Halim Sharar's *Guzashtah Lucknow* as *The Last Phase of an Oriental Culture* was published in 1975. Vipin Krishna's article, "Mapping Linguistic Diffusion in the 1930s: Sulaiman Nadvi and Hindustani," uncovers new ground in the complex terrain of Urdu-Hindi-Hindustani. Siddiqua Fatima's analysis of Krishan Chandar's classic play, *Darwaze Khol Do*, directs our attention to the remarkable genius of Krishan Chander. Translation is vital for the growth and sophistication of language. We have Haris Qadeer's translation of Balraj Manra's iconic short fiction. Amit Julka has rendered Azim Beg Chaghtai's *Wakalat* for English readers. My paper discusses the complexities of

the first verse of Divan-e-Ghalib, and examines some important threads of the discourse-commentary on this famous ghazal.

In the end I want to express my gratitude to all our contributors for responding to our submission call and presenting us with an exciting array of articles. My thanks are due to Professor Arshad Masood Hashmi for inviting me to be the guest editor of this volume. It has been a very rewarding experience. I am indebted to Professor Hashmi for his patience, energy, and diligence in helping me with the editorial process. He was a pillar of support without which the structure would have crumbled.

We hope you will enjoy reading this collection and hope the journal will continue publication. We look forward to hearing from you.

Mehr Afshan Farooqi

Department of Middle Eastern
& South Asian Languages & Cultures
University of Virginia
Charlottesville, USA

That One

Balraj Menra

Translated from Urdu by

Haris Qadeer

When his eyes opened, he was unaware of the time.

He stretched his right hand and picked up a pack of cigarettes from the bedside table, and held one between his lips.

After throwing away the pack of cigarettes, he stretched his hand again and searched for a matchbox.

The matchbox was empty.

He tossed the empty matchbox in the room.

The empty matchbox hit the ceiling and fell to the floor.

He switched on the table lamp.

Four or five matchboxes were lying haphazardly on the bedside table.

One by one, he looked at each of them.

They were all empty.

He threw off the quilt and switched on the light of the room.

It was 2 a.m.

The floor was cold like ice.

It is 2 a.m. now. I was unaware of the time; I was thinking that it was going to be morning soon.

How was my sleep disturbed today at this untimely hour?

Once sleep gets disturbed, it is not possible to get back to it!

He rummaged the entire room.

Book-shelf, trash-bin, trouser-pockets, jacket-pockets ... he did not find a matchbox anywhere.

He overturned every single book but he did not find even a matchstick.

The condition of the room worsened.

Books were lying haphazardly, clothes were lying hither and thither, and the trunk was lying open.

What if anyone visits at this hour?

It is 2 a.m. at night... and such is the condition of the room!

The cigarette was quivering between his lips.

How similar are a lit cigarette and a beating heart!

Where can I find a matchbox?

What if I don't find it ...?

Perhaps...

My beating heart might stop!

How did my sleep get disturbed today at this odd hour!

I was unaware of the time.

It is difficult to sleep again if sleep gets disturbed.

Where can I find a matchbox?

He put a bedsheet on his shoulder and came out of his room.

It was a chilly December night. The darkness ruled and the silence guarded.

He stood in the middle of the road for a few seconds before proceeding in any direction.

When he started walking, he was not familiar with the way.

It was a dark night; it was a silent night. As far as eyes could see, no one was visible.

The dim light of the lampposts was exacerbating the darkness and the silence of the night.

And ...

His feet halted at the crossroad.

There was bright light here as the milky-white tube lights were shining, however, the silence still prevailed as all the shops were closed.

He started moving towards the sweetmeat seller's shop.

It might be possible to find a lump of coal in the furnace – an ember or a piece of half-extinguished ember.

On the platform of the sweetmeat seller's shop, like a bundle, someone was sleeping under a quilt.

No sooner he peeped inside the furnace, the bundle on the platform unbundled.

"Who is that? What are you doing?"

"I am looking for an ember inside the furnace."

"Are you mad? The furnace is cold now!"

"Then what?"

"Then what! Go home!"

"Do you have a matchbox?"

"A matchbox?"

“Yes, I need to light my cigarette.”

“You are insane! Bugger off! Don't disturb my sleep. Go!”

“So, you don't have a matchbox?”

"The owner has the matchbox. He comes in the morning and lights the furnace.. Run along.”

He returned to the road.

The cigarette was quivering between his lips.

He started moving.

The crossway was left behind; the bright lights were left behind – everything was left behind!

He was taking steps at a fast speed.

Lamppost... lamppost... lamppost... countless lampposts were left behind. Dimly lit lampposts – those that darken the darkness and deepen the silence of the night.

All of a sudden, his feet stopped.

Someone was coming from the other direction.

He reached near him and stopped.

“Do you have a matchbox?”

“Matchbox?”

“I need to light my cigarette.”

“No, I don't have a matchbox. I have kept away from this addiction.”

“I thought...”

“What did you think?”

"That you might have a matchbox."

“I don't have a matchbox. I have saved myself from this addiction; I am going to my home, as should you”

He started walking.

The cigarette was quivering between his lips.

He was walking at a slow pace as he was tired.

Unaware of the time, his weary steps were trudging along.

He came across the lampposts; he could see the patches of dim lights followed by darkness. And then again, he could see the lampposts, the patches of dim lights followed by darkness.

Holding the cigarette between his lips, he was taking steps slowly.

The urge to inhale smoke deep down to his lungs had become intense.

His entire body was fatigued.

He was feeling cold in his nightsuit and bedsheet.

He was shivering and was moving slowly with trembling feet. Unaware of time, unaware of the lampposts ...

Once again, his feet halted.

A warning sign was before his eyes.

A bridge was before him – the bridge that needed repair.

A lantern wrapped in red cloth was hanging from a board right in the middle of the road to avoid accidents.

No sooner he took a step to light his cigarette from the wick of the lantern ...

“Who is that?”

He kept mum.

In the darkness, emerging out from some strange layer, a constable pounced on him.

“What were you doing?”

“Nothing...”

“I am asking you, what were you doing?”

“Do you have a matchbox?”

“I am asking you what were you doing there, and you are asking for a matchbox...Who are you?”

“I have to light my cigarette. If you have a matchbox then...!”

"You were doing something here."

“I wanted to light my cigarette with the wick of the lantern...If you have a matchbox ...”

“Who are you ?... Where do you live?”

“I...”

“Where do you live?”

“Model Town!”

“And you need a matchbox...you live in Model Town...Where is Model Town?”

“Model Town!”

He turned and pointed in a direction.

There was darkness as far as eyes could see.

“Come with me to the police station...Model Town...? Model Town is ten miles away from here ... you want a matchbox. Right? You will get it at the police station.”

The constable held his hand.

He went with the constable.

The police station was on the same unending road.

He entered a room of the police station with the constable

In the room, many people were sitting around a big table.

They were all smoking cigarettes.

Many packets of cigarettes and matchboxes were lying on the table.

"Sir, this man was standing near the bridge. He says that he lives in Model Town, and he is asking for a matchbox repeatedly.

"What man!"

"If you permit, may I use your matchbox? I need to light my cigarette."

"Where do you live?"

"Model Town. Can I borrow your matchbox?"

"What do you do?"

"I am a stranger! Can I take the matchbox...?"

"Since when have you been living in Model Town?"

"From three months! ... matchbox ..."

"Matchbox... matchbox... You son of a...! ... weirdo ... return to your home now ... otherwise, I will arrest you ... matchbox ...?"

When he came out of the police station, he was dead tired.

He started trudging through on the unending road.

His nose started running, and his body was giving up.

Smoking is a disease!

Why am I nurturing this disease?

Where will I find a matchbox?

What if I don't find it?

He was unaware of the time; he was unaware of the lampposts; he was unaware of the road; he was unaware of his own body!

He was stumbling and was moving ahead.

His tottering feet exhibited some sort of intoxication.

Morning broke; he halted for a moment.

He stopped for a moment and controlled himself.

He controlled himself, and as he was about to take a step ...

Someone was coming from the other direction; his steps were tottering.

He came and stopped near him.

A cigarette was quivering between his lips.

“Do you have a matchbox?”

“Matchbox?”

“So, you don't have a matchbox?”

“Even I was looking for a match....”

He walked away without listening to what he has to say.

Ahead, in the same direction from where he had just come.

He took his step.

Ahead, in the direction from where he had come.

—

First published as “Woh” in *Surkh-o-Siyah* (Ed. By Sarwarul Hoda, Educational Publishing House, Delhi, 2004)